

Diamagnetic Susceptibilities of Tin in Di and Tetra Valency States.

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Tin occurs in three different forms. Grey tin is cubic in structure while white tin is tetragonal. Further, white tin when cooled passes into the grey variety and when heated above 161° changes into the γ -phase. Honda (*Ann. Physik*, 1910, **32**, 1027) in his classical researches on the thermomagnetic properties of elements, has shown that white tin is paramagnetic, while grey tin is diamagnetic. He has further shown that the susceptibility of white tin undergoes a decrease on melting. Honda's work was further continued by Owen (*ibid.*, 1912, **37**, 657) who also found that white tin is paramagnetic ($\chi = +0.02 \times 10^{-6}$) and grey tin is diamagnetic ($\chi = -0.255 \times 10^{-6}$). Recently Ramchandra Rao (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sciences*, 1934, **1**, 123) has found that on powdering white tin becomes diamagnetic. Whether the change obtained by Rao is due to a change in the particle size or the conversion of tin into another allotropic modification due to pressure and temperature during the process of powdering, is a controversial matter. It appears, however, probable that a thermomagnetic investigation of the tin salts may throw some light on this unique behaviour of tin. Also a very desirable investigation would be the accurate determination of susceptibilities of tin ions in various valency states.

This publication deals with the last two aspects of the magneto-chemistry of the tin ion.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The ionic susceptibilities in the dissolved state have been determined by the aid of a modified form of Decker's balance (Bhatnagar, Nevgi and Tuli, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1934, **9**, 311). In order to determine the susceptibilities at different temperatures, the portion of the tube between the upper stop-cock and the glass window is double-jacketted with an inlet and outlet for the circulation of water at different temperatures. The specific susceptibility in the dissolved state has been calculated according to the equation

$$\chi_L = \frac{\phi_L \left[\frac{\chi_w - \chi_a}{\phi_w - \phi_a} \right] + \left[\frac{\chi_a \phi_w - \chi_w \phi_a}{\phi_w - \phi_a} \right]}{d}$$

where χ_L , χ_a and χ_w denote respectively the mass susceptibility of the solution, of air and water; ϕ_L , ϕ_a and ϕ_w denote the angle of torsion due to the solution, air and water respectively and d denotes the density of the solution.

The susceptibility of the salt from that of the solution has been calculated with the help of the relation,

$$\chi_L = \chi_{\text{salt}} \times C_{\text{salt}} + \chi_{\text{solvent}} \times (1 - C_{\text{salt}})$$

where C_{salt} denotes the concentration of the salt in solution.

The specific susceptibility of the salts in the solid state has been determined by a suitably modified form of Gouy's balance (*cf.* Nevgi, *Current Science*, 1935, 4, 403). For higher temperature measurements, an electric oven made of mica pieces and nicrom wire was used. According to the theory of this instrument, the susceptibilities can be calculated from the following equation.

$$\chi_{d_1} = \frac{\tau}{m_{d_1}} \left\{ (\chi_{d_1} m_{d_1} - \chi_a m_{a d_1}) \frac{W_{d_2}}{W_{d_1}} + \chi_a m_{a d_1} \right\}$$

where χ_a , χ_{d_1} and χ_{d_2} denote respectively the mass susceptibility of the medium (air), of the diamagnetic substance d_1 , and d_2 ; m_{d_1} , m_{d_2} , denote masses of d_1 and d_2 , and $m_{a d_1}$ and $m_{a d_2}$, that of air displaced by d_1 and d_2 .

Estimation of the Purity of the Substances.

All the substances, which were used in this investigation, were extra pure. However, qualitative and quantitative analyses were always undertaken to test their purity. Only those substances which proved to be quite pure after going through this exhaustive process of analysis were employed for the magnetic measurements. A few of them had to be prepared in the laboratory.

The balance was tested against standard substances before its use in this investigation and the results obtained are given below.

TABLE I.

Substance.	$-\chi \times 10^{-6}$ at 25°.	$-\chi \times 10^{-6}$ at 60°.
NaCl	0.494	0.496
Aniline	0.688	0.690
Nitrobenzene	0.505	0.509

TABLE II.

Tin salts in the solid form.

Substance.	$-\chi \times 10^{-6}$ at 25°.	$-\chi \times 10^{-6}$ at 80°	$-\chi \times 10^{-6}$ (from Tables).
Stannous chloride	0.363	0.372	0.37
Stannic bromide	0.356	0.365	0.354
Stannic iodide	0.328	0.337	0.32
Stannous oxalate	0.251	0.264	0.25

TABLE III.

Tin salts from solutions (tried on Decker's balance).

Substance.	$-\chi \times 10^{-6}$ at 25°.	$-\chi \times 10^{-6}$ at 60°.
Stannous chloride	0.381	0.360
Stannic chloride	0.429	0.41
Stannic iodide	0.341	0.323

The ionic values of the negative radicals which are taken from the different authors are given below.

TABLE IV.

Bromine.	Iodine.	Chlorine.
-32.5×10^{-6} (Reichender)	-45×10^{-6} (Pascal)	-22.1×10^{-6} (Kido)
-31.4×10^{-6} (Farquharson)	-20.1×10^{-6} (Pascal)
.....	-19.85×10^{-6} (Bhatnagar)

TABLE V.

The ionic values of tin.

Substance.	Ion.	Sources of the negative radical values.	Ionic values $-\chi \times 10^{-6}$.
SnBr ₄	Sn ^{IV}	{ Reichender	26.0
		{ Farquharson	30.5
SnI ₄	Sn ^{IV}	Pascal	25.5
SnCl ₂	Sn ^{II}	{ Kido	24.67
		{ Pascal	28.67
		{ Bhatnagar	29.17
Stannous oxalate	Sn ^{II}	Pascal	22.9

DISCUSSION.

From a perusal of the above described results, it is evident that many interesting points arise. The general expression of the ionic susceptibility is

$$\chi_{\text{ion}} = - \frac{Ne^2}{6M C^2} \sum_n \bar{r}^2 \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

Slater (*Phys. Rev.*, 1930, **36**, 58) gave the following value for the radical part of the wave function of a single electron,

$$\psi = r^{(n'-1)} e^{-\left\{ \frac{(z-s)}{n'} \right\} r}$$

and calculated the mean square radius of the inert gases by the equation

$$\bar{r}^2 = \frac{n'^2 (n' + \frac{1}{2}) (n' + 1)}{(Z - S)^2}$$

where n' is the effective principle quantum number and $(Z-S)$, the effective nuclear charge. The electrons are divided into the following groups: 1s; 2s, p; 3s, p; 3d; 4s, p; 4d; 4f; etc. The screening constants are 0.35 for electrons in the same group (except for 1s electrons, where 0.30 is used); 0.85 and 1.0 for s and p electrons where $n = n_0 - 1$ and $N < N_0 - 1$ respectively. For d and f electrons, the value 1.0 should be taken for all electrons in the lower groups. After finding out the different values of \bar{r}^2 for all the electrons in an ion, the value of $\sum_n \bar{r}^2$ is substituted in equation (i) and the ionic value is determined.

The value of Sn^{IV} ion which belongs to the complete ionic configuration, has been calculated by Pauling (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, **A114**, 181), Slater (*loc. cit.*), and Angus (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1932, **A136**, 569) but the value of Sn^{II} does not seem to have been calculated. The rules followed by Slater (*loc. cit.*) and Angus (*loc. cit.*), although strictly valid for the configurations of complete ions, have been frequently employed to explain the magnetic behaviour of the ions which have not got the complete configuration. Accordingly an attempt has been made to calculate the value of Sn^{II} ion also.

According to the scheme given above the ionic value of Sn^{II} comes out to be -38.247×10^{-6} . Recently Angus calculated the ionic value by taking into consideration a small difference in the screening constants of s and p electrons of the same quantum number. According to his formula the ionic value of Sn^{II} should be -38.165×10^{-6} . In

the following tables, the experimental and theoretical ionic values of Sn^{II} and Sn^{IV} are given as calculated from the results obtained here along with those given in the International Critical Tables. While calculating these values, the question of taking the correct values of the negative radicals comes in, but there is so great a discord between the values given by different authors that it has been found desirable to calculate the ionic susceptibilities by subtracting the different values of the negative ions from their molecular susceptibilities and bring into prominence their great divergence.

TABLE VI.

The ionic susceptibility of Sn^{IV} .

Substance.	Source.	The values of negative ions and their sources.	Ionic value $\chi \times 10^{-6}$.
EXPERIMENTAL.			
SnBr_4	The present authors	$\text{Br} = \begin{cases} -32.5 & \text{Reichender} \\ -31.4 & \text{Farquharson} \\ 34.7 & \text{Kido} \end{cases}$	$\begin{matrix} -26.0 \\ -30.5 \\ -17.3 \end{matrix}$
SnI_4	The present authors	$\text{I} = \begin{cases} -45.0 & \text{Pascal} \\ -49.25 & \text{Ikenmeyer} \\ 53.2 & \text{Kido} \end{cases}$	$\begin{matrix} -25.5 \\ -8.5 \\ +7.3 \end{matrix}$
$\text{SnO}(\text{OH})_2$	International	Critical Tables	-28.0
$\text{Sn}(\text{OH})_4$	International	Critical Tables	-34.4
$\text{SnO}(\text{OH})\text{CH}_3$	International	Critical Tables	-28.1
THEORETICAL.			
	Slater	...	-23.838
	Angus	...	-23.755
	Pauling	...	-28.0

TABLE VII.

The ionic susceptibility of Sn^{II} .

Substance.	Source.	Values of the negative ions and their sources.	Ionic susceptibility $\chi \times 10^{-6}$.
EXPERIMENTAL.			
SnCl_2	Present authors	$\text{Cl} = \begin{cases} -22.1 & \text{Kido} \\ -20.1 & \text{Pascal} \\ -19.85 & \text{Bhatnagar} \end{cases}$	$\begin{matrix} -24.67 \\ -28.67 \\ -29.17 \end{matrix}$
Stannous oxalate	"	$\text{COO} \begin{matrix} \\ \text{COO} \end{matrix} = -0.29$ Pascal	-22.9
SnSO_4	Int. Crit. Tables	$\text{SO}_4 = \begin{cases} -31.4 & \text{Int. Crit. Tables} \\ -39.0 & \text{Kido} \end{cases}$	$\begin{matrix} -28.75 \\ -21.15 \end{matrix}$
THEORETICAL.			
	Slater's method	...	-38.247
	Angus' method	...	-38.165

From a survey of these tables it appears that the values of Sn^{IV} lie between 25.5 and 30.5 derived from the experimental results obtained here as against the theoretical values of 23.838, 23.755 and 28.0. The mean value of 25.5 and 30.5 comes out to be 28. This closely corresponds with the Pauling's value of 28. The values obtained by Slater and Angus are slightly lower. This difference seems to be due to the different values assigned to the negative ions. The ionic susceptibilities for Sn^{IV} lie between 22.9 and 29.17. This is quite different from the theoretical values 38.247 and 38.165. It has been clearly pointed out by Angus and Kido that a disappointing feature of diamagnetic measurements is the lack of agreement between the results obtained by different authors who have investigated the same substance. This would become more evident from an examination of Table VIII which shows the divergence in the values of χ for various negative ions commonly reported in literature, and in the International Critical Tables.

TABLE VIII.

Diamagnetic ionic values of some common negative ions.

Author.	F.	Cl.	Br.	I.	SO_4 .
THEORETICAL.					
Pauling	8.1	29.0	54.0	80.0	51.0
Slater	8.3	25.79	40.1	59.83	...
Angus	7.25	22.86	36.65	55.32	...
Stoner	17.3	40.4	32.0
EXPERIMENTAL.					
Kido	12.2	22.1	34.7	53.2	39.0
Ikenmeyer	13.9	20.4	34.8	49.25	...
Pascal	5.95	20.1	30.5	45.0	...
Bhatnagar	...	19.85
Reichender	...	21.9	32.5
Weiss	...	23.9	33.9	49.5	...
Farquharson	31.4
Int. Crit. Tables	31.4

Influence of Temperature.

From a survey of Table II it is evident that the diamagnetism of the tin salts increases with temperature. It has been shown by Honda that white tin decreases in its paramagnetism and becomes diamagnetic on melting. He has explained this phenomenon on the assumption that the magnetic susceptibility can be given by an expression

$$\chi = \chi_d + \chi_p$$

where χ_p and χ_d refer to the paramagnetic and diamagnetic contributions towards the susceptibility χ . χ_p has got a tendency to decrease with the rise of temperature. Consequently χ will increase in its diamagnetism. Recently Van Vleck (*Phys. Rev.*, 1928, **31**, 587; 1932, **14**, 1015), by the system of quantum mechanics, has developed an expression for molecular magnetism which can be written as

$$\chi = P_x + P_y - D$$

where P_x is paramagnetic dependent on temperature, P_y is a weak paramagnetic independent of temperature and D is pure diamagnetic. In substance where P_x is important, χ can have a tendency to increase in its diamagnetism with temperature. It seems probable that the increment obtained here with temperature might be due to the paramagnetic constituents of tin.

Solutions.

The diamagnetic values, recorded in Table III, for SnCl_2 , SnCl_4 and SnI_4 in the dissolved state are slightly higher than those in the solid state. At higher temperatures, the diamagnetism of these salts in the dissolved state decreases to a certain extent. These changes, that have been observed here, can be attributed to some complex formation. Evidence in favour of complex formations is given below separately for each salt.

SnCl₂ in Hydrochloric acid Solution.—Water and hydrochloric acid play an important part in the formation of complexes with SnCl_2 independently or combined. According to the magnetic observations of Hoccard (*Compt. rend.*, 1929, **188**, 1151), Farquharson (*Phil. Mag.*, 1931, **12**, 283) and Scott and Blair (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, **35**, 475), hydrochloric acid solutions of various concentrations themselves do not follow the mixture law. Engel (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1888, *ii*, **50**, 96) has shown that SnCl_2 combines with hydrochloric acid solution forming HSnCl_3 , $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. SnCl_2 is said to form hydrates with one, two or

four molecules of water in which dihydrate is the compound best known. Secondly, SnCl_2 itself exists in different forms under different conditions and in different solvents. SnCl_2 exists in the form of Sn_2Cl_4 in the vapour state as its vapour density is distinctly higher than the theoretical value. According to A. Werner (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1897, **15**, 1) the molecular weight of SnCl_2 is 202.8 in pyridine and 176 in ethyl sulphide while the calculated value is 189. Schröder and Steiner (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1909, *ii*, **49**, 63) found that the molecular weight is half the normal value in dilute solution of SnCl_2 in boiling methyl acetate. The freezing method of SnCl_2 in urethane (Castoro, *Gazzetta*, 1898, **28**, 317) shows that the molecular weight of SnCl_2 is normal. These facts point out the existence of different forms of SnCl_2 under different conditions and in different solvents. Thirdly, solution has got the tendency of absorbing oxygen from the atmosphere. The changes that are obtained may, therefore, be due to the above stated complexes.

SnCl_4 Solution in Water.—Union of SnCl_4 with water is attended by the development of heat, contraction in volume and the formation of several hydrates of SnCl_4 with water, amongst which $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are well known. $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is stable between 19° and 56° ; $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ between 56° and 63° and $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ between 63° and 83° . Kahlenberg and Lincoln (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1899, **3**, 12) have found that SnCl_4 undergoes molecular association in some organic solvents. The decrease that is obtained here can be very easily explained on the view of the breaking up of these associations at higher temperatures.

SnI_4 Solution in Benzene.—The suitable solvent found for SnI_4 is benzene. SnI_4 is hydrolysed in water, and the other solvents such as CS_2 , ether and chloroform have very low boiling points. These solvents cannot, therefore, be used here. Personne (*Compt. rend.*, 1862, **54**, 216) has noted that SnI_4 shows complex formation in benzene also. The decrease obtained at higher temperatures can, therefore, be attributed to breaking up of these complexes.